

Towards seamless collaboration of humans and high-payload robots: An automotive case study

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ABSTRACT

Despite the ergonomic challenges that large-sized product assemblies underlay for human operators, related processes are deselected from hybrid automation mostly due to the payload limitations of collaborative robots. Driven by industrial requirements for ergonomic and performance improvement, this paper presents the implementation of a human-high payload robot symbiotic workstation and discusses the key enabling technologies for seamless collaboration, namely: a) a multi-modal human-robot interaction pipeline, b) a gesture based contactless manual guidance module, c) fenceless safety monitoring system and logic, and d) an augmented reality-based training application for operator inclusion. An automotive case study is used for validating the complete hybrid system's usability and performance besides improved operator ergonomics and well-being. This work's findings prove that high-payload robots can support operators through intuitive means of interaction and businesses can rely on collaborative systems for improved performance metrics and job openness.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the market's needs for shorter product life cycles and product customization are met with the introduction of advanced tools and technologies of the Industry 4.0 [1] that are trying to balance cost, flexibility, quality and time [2]. In most cases, hybrid cells and Human Robot Collaboration (HRC) assembly lines appear to achieve this balance by combining positive attributes of human workers and robots [3]. The merging of flexibility, improvisation and dexterity of operators, on one hand, with the tireless robot productivity and repeatability, on the other, showcases a great potential for automation and improvement of working conditions. In this regard, there are numerous paradigms of fenceless hybrid production systems that have been deployed or prototyped in industrial sectors such as composites [4], automotive [5,6], white goods [7], and others.

In collaborative manufacturing systems, operators can work side by side with robots in close proximity and share resources or even tasks in fenceless workstations. However, with this fenceless coexistence emerges confusion and challenges in terms of task assignment, interaction, adaptive control and safety that can lead to low acceptance of such solutions [8]. In the last decade, significant research effort has been put on addressing those challenges and pushing standardization to new

frontiers for unlocking HRC's full potential.

This paper discusses the implementation of a human robot collaboration system by suggesting the usage of high-payload robots; for assisting human operators in assembly operations involving heavy-weight components. Even though large sized assemblies usually underlay many challenges for workers, such processes are deselected from semi-automation due to the payload limitations of collaborative robots. The novelty of this work leans on the combination of miscellaneous technologies under the baseline of achieving human acceptance and well-being. Among others, in this paper four integral modules are analyzed towards the achievement of seamless close collaboration, namely: a) a personalized multi-modal interaction pipeline (MMIP), b) a dynamically reconfigurable safety monitoring system and logic, c) a contactless gesture-based manual guidance system, and d) an Augmented Reality (AR)-based training application for worker adaptation. Those technologies attain to synthesize a safe, intuitive and personalized working environment promoting job openness and well-being. Driven by an automotive use-case, that offered a fertile ground for performance and usability assessment of this system, a series of industrial requirements motivated the development and implementation of those technologies. However, the discussed design methodologies can be used as a solid baseline for similar applications that involve humans

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and cooperative industrial high-payload or lightweight robots.

This manuscript is organized in seven sections, including this introductory section. [Section 2](#) provides an overview of the state-of-the-art on HRC, emphasizing on aspects such as the design, communication interfaces, manual guidance, safety and training. In [Section 3](#), a complete description of the approach behind overall system and its submodules is given, towards the implementation of the collaborative workcell in situ. [Section 4](#) touches upon the implementation of the main modules' prototypes and their deployment on the collaborative cell. An industrial case study that was used for evaluating the performance of the integrated system is presented in [Section 5](#), whereas the obtained results are discussed in [Section 6](#). The paper concludes in [Section 7](#), where paper's scientific and industrial contributions besides the author's future activities are outlined.

2. Relevant work

This section discusses the state of the art and previous work findings in a number of topics around the implementation of HRC solutions. As discussed in [\[9\]](#), a collaborative workstation must be an open workspace where the human and the robot can collaborate and take decisions, towards the execution of a task; in a healthy, safe and ergonomic-wise manner. This requires fenceless coexistence with automatic transitioning of the available safety modes without any risks or conflicts. This can be achieved by natural communication between those resources as well as direct control of the robot by the human.

Starting from the design of the symbiotic workstation itself, the definition of the layout arrangement is a quite complex topic, due to its large variability and risk involved. It is important that the positioning of robot, or the arrangement of the collaborative and human working areas leaves sufficient safety distances as declared by the ISO-15066 [\[10\]](#). Through the years, different methodologies and design considerations for HRC have been published [\[11–15\]](#), that propose alternative collaboration schemes, safety concepts, workpiece handling methods or even automated layout generating tools [\[16\]](#). It is evident, that the specifications of each industrial scenario, in combination with the required skills for the execution of the process have a great impact on the overall collaboration framework. This framework is mostly affected by the levels of interaction between the human and the robot. Previous work [\[11,17,18\]](#) and standards [\[10\]](#) classify those levels in an attempt to highlight the different interaction, safety and workstation design requirements.

The conceptualization of a fenceless environment and its interaction levels depends on the proposed process plan. What operations, in what order, how and by which resources are going to be executed is a problem with numerous solutions. A common practice is to rather automate strenuous and repeatable operations than dexterous and proficient ones [\[8\]](#). In this regard, effort is given on different planning methodologies for achieving efficient and safe collaboration. In [\[19\]](#), a planner that considers both precedence constraints, real-time human intentions, workspace status, etc., while attempting human satisfaction, is presented. Alternative coordination and planning methods suggest data driven decision-making systems [\[20\]](#), hybrid hierarchical workload models [\[21\]](#), prediction of future system evolution based on Petri Nets [\[22\]](#), etc.

Apart from the high-level decision making, a great number of studies tries to expand robot cognition capabilities for improving efficiency and granting safety. By implementing perception systems that can monitor operator's behavior, robots are able to on-line adjust their trajectories and activities. In [\[23\]](#), real-time proximity queries for safety strategies are investigated by implementing swept sphere bounding volumes for ensuring the safety of the workers in close immediacy to the robots. In the same vein [\[24\]](#), the data from multiple 3D imaging sensors of different modalities are combined into a volumetric evidence grid and are segmented into regions corresponding to background, people, and robots. Upon region overlapping, the robot responds with a safeguard

stop until the issue is resolved. A different scenario suggests dynamic reconfiguration of safety zones upon their violation, and the update of robot velocity and distance [\[25\]](#). One handicap of most collision-free motion planners is that despite the capability of safeguarding operator's integrity, they cannot preserve Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) consistency. Thus, more advanced context-aware collision free motion planning [\[26\]](#) have been proposed in order to address those issues by using learning-based algorithms.

The full potential of an efficient workstation design, safety logic, or decision-making system can't be reached if the involved agents are not able to bilaterally communicate. On the other hand, operators' sense of safety depends on the support received by the system, as well as the awareness about robot's actions. Research has elaborated on human robot interaction (HRI) technologies for seamless collaboration and communication by developing a variety of human machine interfaces (HMIs) or by establishing multi-modal interaction bridges. In the era of cyber-physical systems, a technology with great interest for HRI is Augmented Reality (AR). AR overlays digital information on the physical world and provides intuitive presentation of data and knowledge [\[27\]](#). Different wearable and non-wearable devices have also been used in HRC applications for communicating task instructions, robot trajectories and safety zones besides offering a plethora of direct robot controls [\[7\]](#). A recapitulation of the requirements of the human workforce communication and a systematic context-aware multi-modal interaction framework is presented in [\[28\]](#). Recent studies also worked on the personalization of the HRI communication bridges through the selection of the used modalities and the customization of the available interfaces [\[29\]](#). In [\[30\]](#), a function block based multi-modal controlling framework is presented, where event-driven function blocks are used as reusable functions for communication and robot control; using haptics, gestures and voice inputs. An expansion of this function block approach proposes the usage of human electroencephalography brainwaves for direct robot control using neural networks [\[31\]](#). Given the advances in computational performance and training methods, there is also increased interest for voice control schemes [\[32\]](#), as well as human gesture and pose identification methods [\[33\]](#) due to the hands-free operation and similarity with bilateral human interactions. A special type of human robot communication, that is also considered as a distinct interaction type, is hand guiding or manual robot guidance. This mean requires an external human monitoring system, that generates controlling inputs as the operator guides the manipulator accurately. Through the years, different methods have been implemented involving force data [\[7,34\]](#), visual data [\[35\]](#), haptics [\[30\]](#), etc. In overall, such systems are favored in applications where robots lack the required cognition for accurate or dynamic positioning (e.g., during part joining).

Despite the benefits of aforementioned technologies, those are not widely found in factory shopfloors. Apart their certification, the most common challenge is the technology acceptance by operators. In an era of shorter product lifecycles, operators are also stressed to keep up with frequent product and production system changes. In parallel, modern manufacturing systems are data depended, meaning that operators are exposed to large information volumes, and they must strictly follow the monitoring processes. Subsequently, an integral area that also needs optimization is operator training. In this direction, previous work includes pioneer training frameworks based on augmented reality [\[36\]](#), simulation [\[37\]](#), and virtual reality [\[38\]](#). Previous findings indicate that these frameworks have to be human-centric and follow a "gamification" approach [\[39\]](#) for more efficient learning.

3. Approach

When designing and developing a collaborative workstation, certain parameters deriving from industry, regulations, as well as results of relevant activities, need to be taken into consideration. As presented in [Fig. 1](#), the followed approach, for introducing a fenceless hybrid workstation, consists of a workflow for the analysis, design, implementation

Fig. 1. Action flow during a human-robot collaboration work cell development.

and commissioning activities. Those activities form a closed-loop process towards the achievement of all design specifications. Despite the fact that this manuscript discusses the implementation of a human high-payload collaborative system for the automotive industry, the generality and applicability of the approach is not compromised.

The basis of automating an industrial manufacturing process can be found in aspects where human workers are more susceptible to (i.e., repeatability, physical strain, etc.). Thus, automation or hybrid frameworks need to be implemented in a production line when it is evident that those can relieve existing operators from musculoskeletal strain, fatigue and tendency to errors. Key Performance Indicators (e.g., cycle time, efficiency, quality, cost, etc.) and ergonomic evaluation methods can highlight which production line workstations have improvement potential (Step0).

Given an industrial case with a number of specifications and aspects to be optimized, the next step is the definition of the optimized system's schedule or, in other words, its sequence of operations (Step1). This activity aims [1] on conceptualizing an efficient way of achieving the desired results by dictating parameters such as resource capabilities, resource availability, product variant constraints, regulations, cycle time, cost, ergonomics etc. For human robot collaboration systems, important aspects, that affect this conceptualization, are the required dexterity and physical handling capabilities per task. The most common approach is allocating tasks of high repeatability, heavy workpiece handling and low dexterity to robot agents whereas operators are assigned to execute tasks of high dexterity, good ergonomics or high improvisation needs. The completion of this step leads to the definition of the hybrid solution's process plan.

By having a process plan available, the next step involves the generation of a collaborative layout where all resources, tools, fixtures, sensors, equipment etc. are defined and placed in the working area of interest (Step2). Design principles for those activities are numerous but the baseline is that operator's comfort and safety must be ensured [6]. On the other hand, spatial arrangement and dimensioning of the workplace have to promote seamless collaboration without unexpected robot stops. For this work, working areas are classified as "robot", "human" or "collaborative" depending on the interference of resources (i.e., human, robot) within them. The spatial arrangement of those areas follows a smooth progression, meaning that workstations are rather grouped per type than been alternated. Subsequently, safety zones boundary changes are less frequent, and chances of unintentional intrusions are limited. At this stage, the safety regulations and norms are considered for the design and dimensioning of all resources. Given the resources available in a digital format, a representation of the conceptual collaborative framework can take place. This computer aided representation highlights any engineering errors and faults, but it can also clarify if industrial and regulation requirements are addressed upon simulation (Step3).

If simulation results highlight deficiencies (e.g., KPIs, ergonomics, safety, etc.), the aforementioned conceptualization step is repeated by

using the simulation's findings as additional specifications. In case redesign and virtual recommissioning are not sufficient to overcome those issues, then a new process plan is required. Upon the achievement of virtual commissioning, the deployment activities for interaction technologies, safety logic, system engineering, etc. focus on delivering each required submodule and on its integration on the rest of the hybrid system (Step4). By the end of this step, a physical collaborative cell will be implemented. Prior industrial implementation, risk assessment and finally verification of the solution based on end-user's requirements, needs to take place (Step5).

The following sections elaborate on the design, development and implementation of the system's main modules for seamless human robot collaboration. Apart from the implementation of the system itself, significant effort is given on how unexperienced operators can easily adapt on a hybrid environment by designing a training framework for cyber-physical systems. Resource and layout design aspects are not extensively analyzed as they are out of the scope of this manuscript.

3.1. Multi-modal human robot interaction

Lack of an efficient communication pipeline can lead to low productivity, hazardous situations, and hardware stress due to frequent safeguard stops. Moreover, challenges in the familiarization of operators with different background experiences, lack of trust or even sense of fear can affect commissioning in a negative way or even cancel industrial integration [8]. This section discusses the approach behind the implementation of a personalized multi-modal Interaction Pipeline (MMIP). Two sub-sections are used for separating the means of cognitive communication (i.e. nonphysical means intended for synchronization, monitoring and support) with the one mean that is dedicated on direct robot motion control.

3.1.1. Multi-modal interfaces for human robot interaction

The proposed system multi-modal interaction pipeline is designed to communicate information about: a) robot activities, b) operator activities, c) hybrid cell status, d) key resources' status, e) assembly operation itself, and interprets tools for direct robot control. The novelty of this interaction pipeline lays in its capability to communicate this information by different means in terms of end-devices (e.g., beacons, led, wearables, etc.), application environments (i.e., scenes for novice or advanced operators) and modalities (e.g., sound, visuals, touch, voice, etc.). This is achieved through a multi-layer architecture where bilateral information streams take place. The highest level interprets the interface's broker that acts both as a client and a server depending on the direction of information flow. The intermediate layer comprises all available end-devices and their user interfaces. Each device connects to the broker and makes available a number of interaction modalities depending on their hardware specifications. All available modals constitute the bottom layer of this framework and include each interface that takes advantage of human's senses (e.g., hearing, touch, voice, etc.)

towards cognitive interaction. This architecture, as depicted in Fig. 2, suggests that the intermediate and bottom layers are isolated from the rest of the system and its communication middleware. This allows adding and removing of end-devices without affecting the rest of system’s performance, thus increasing robustness against device failures or autonomy limitations (i.e., battery). In addition, the introduction of end-device applications that are not compatible with the commonly applied system’s middleware does not necessitate heavy modifications and restructuring of the system. Instead, a communication bridge only with the MMIP broker is sufficient. Finally, an additional benefit of such architecture could be the expansion of the broker by adding processing modules in case the end-devices lack computational performance for edge computing. In that sense, those devices will be limited to “remote rendering” of outputs and communication of inputs.

The MMIP’s broker and the internal network is structured to manage information streams back and forth the end-devices. More specifically, in case of Human to System (HS) interaction, each end-device application is responsible for fusing data originating from the used input modality and generating knowledge. This knowledge is then forwarded to the broker, where the former one communicates it via standard ROS [40] messages to the rest of the system. In contrary, for System to Human (SH) interaction, the opposite process takes place where system’s resources or modules communicate information to the MMIP broker through ROS. The broker passes this information to all end-devices in parallel using the established bridges. Each connected device is responsible for exposing this information to the operator based on its specification modalities. This means that the operator can have access on the same message, instruction, etc., from multiple interfaces or means and consider only the most appealing one(s).

The redundancy in interaction modalities can provide many benefits (i.e., overcoming of autonomy issues, clarified requests, awareness, satisfaction of user preferences, etc.) however, it could create information overflow and user fatigue as well. For this reason, the personalization of the interaction pipeline is feasible through: a) the customization of each application environment, and b) the deployment and usage of the desired end-devices. Customization is achieved by creating operator profiles that store and retrieve operator’s preferences through parameters in the system’s database. This way, the interaction pipeline can be moderated to meet the user’s experience and needs while maintaining productivity at the highest level possible. Novice operators may request richer information about the robot status and the assembly process in order to feel confident and comfortable. In contrary, skilled users may feel distracted by huge information volumes and they might need very lean support for reaching the same trust and assurance levels.

Thus, every application interprets an “Options” tab where functionalities and modalities can be enabled or omitted.

Table 1 summarizes the types of information that are exchanged during HS or SH interaction through the proposed framework

3.1.2. Manual guidance

In many cases, manufacturing operations require close human robot interaction in the form of “guiding the robot to an apposite position”. In this work, a contactless gesture-based manual guidance (MG) system is designed for allowing operators to fine-tune the position of the robot’s end-effector during transferring and assembly processes. By monitoring the hand gestures and spatial coordinates, a “gesture” modality is established that is used for controlling the position of the manipulator. The module interprets an optical sensor, a manual guidance client and a robot routine acting as a server (Fig. 3). The optical sensor is mounted on the robot’s end-effector and is responsible for capturing the operator’s hand coordinates relative to the sensor. The manual guidance client normalizes and filters the hand coordinate data before forwarding them to the robot routine for executing the appropriate “hand following” trajectory.

Table 1 Multi-Modal Interaction Pipeline types of exchanged information.

Exchanged information	Description
Intuitive assembly instructions	MMIP provides intuitive instructions about the executed task on each available front-end application. According to the available modalities, those instructions could be in the form of text, figures, arrows, animations, holograms, etc., through visual 2D or augmented 3D instances.
Robot-centric information	MMIP provides information about the robot status (e.g., moving, stopped, etc.), its executed action, the planned and executed trajectory as well as the safety zone configurations. Given the available end-devices, such robot-centric information is communicated in the form of audio, 2D visuals or 3D augmented notifications, lines, warnings, etc.
Human-centric information	If a real-time ergonomic evaluation system is implemented, the interfaces transmit the results via: a) traffic light indications, b) detailed human skeleton represented with segments colored under the same color traffic light coding, and c) reports where aforementioned results are associated with the executed task.
System Human interaction	Voice, touch, or gesture modals can be used for notifying the system about the completion of a human task or for direct robot control (e.g., pause a motion, start a motion, manual guidance, etc.)

Fig. 2. Multi Modal Interaction Pipeline overall architecture.

Fig. 3. Gesture based manual guidance flow chart.

Operator's integrity is ensured by setting a number of thresholds and conditions during the manual guidance process. Those thresholds safeguard that there will be no robot movements unless the tracking inputs are reliable and the outputs (i.e., robot trajectories) cannot lead to a hazardous scenario. More specifically, the trustworthiness of inputs is ensured by prerequiring gestures as an "enabling" switch before monitoring the coordinates of user's palm. In addition, the client monitors the status of the tracking sensor and doesn't communicate data in the case of noise or sensor timeout. Furthermore, gestures and palm coordinates are considered only from a specific area of the sensor's field of view. Focusing on the robot agent, the manual guidance server is only enabled when the program executor dispatches to the robot controller the specific manual guidance related subprograms. In parallel, the manual guidance routine can be enabled only when the robot is set on "collaborative mode" to guarantee that close and high levels of interaction take place only when the robot parameters are set to lower than safe limits for close quarter coexistence. The flowchart of Fig. 3 illustrates the operation of the proposed manual guidance framework. It is clarified that the original objective was the implementation of hybrid controller that also uses Force Torque (F/T) data as inputs. This would allow the establishment of additional thresholds that would limit the resulted forces during the peg in hole process besides bound any human actions that could lead to collisions and part damage. Given the hardware availability at the moment of writing this paper, the authors elaborate on the implemented prototype that is based solely on visual input.

3.2. Safe human robot coexistence

According to the international legislation (ISO/TS 15066, ISO 10218-1,2)[10,41,42], four fundamental collaborative methods have been specified based on the level of human-robot interaction, which are applied in each robotic application accordingly based on a risk assessment:

- Speed and separation monitoring (SSM), where the robot's movements and speed are adjusted according to the human-robot relative distance.
- Safety-rated monitored stop (SMS), where the robot stops if a human enters the collaborative workcell and resumes its tasks when the human walks out.
- Hand guiding (HG), where the robot performs controlled tasks under human handling.
- Power and force limiting (PFL), where the robot limits the exerted force when in contact with human.

In case of a safety function violation or incompliance with the

thresholds, according to the IEC 60204-1 [43], a controlled stop of robot's actuation is triggered. There are three types of categories stops, distinguished by whether the power supply is removed or not, as follows:

- Category 0 stop: Stop by immediate removal of power supply to the robot's actuators
- Category 1 stop: Stop with power supply still available to the robot's actuators till standstill and then power is removed
- Category 2 stop: Controlled stop with power supply still transduced to the actuators

For the implemented human robot collaboration system, after the conceptualization of an indicative layout, the required safety functions per task were enlisted. A simulation environment was used for the virtual commissioning of the system before the implementation of the physical cell. Finally, a risk assessment was performed at the implemented solution and any safety hazards are identified. Except traditional and standard practices, additional features are going to be examined and implemented. At first, interaction without physical barriers is attained, thus a certified 3D camera system is introduced to track the human-robot relative distance and send feedback to the robot's controller accordingly. Different safety zone arrangements that scan the working area are dynamically updated based on the operation status and the robot position. Secondly, for increasing the operator's awareness and mitigating safeguard stops or robot speed reduction, those safety zone arrangements are visible in real time to the operator in holographic form. In addition to the safety zone arrangements, the current robot trajectory is also displayed through different modalities. The goal is informing operators about the followed robot path and avoiding any unwanted collisions or intrusions. Subsequently, the implemented safety strategy acts: a) proactively, by avoiding probable collisions through intuitive communication of safety related information, and b) reactively, by controlling robot speed in case of safety zone violations.

Apart from the physical safety aspects, the whole system is cybersecurity hardened and designed to detect and mitigate a wide range of security threats. The "prevention" and "detection" policies of this system are out of the scope of this publication. Those suggest a series of policies and best practices for limiting the exposure of the system to external threats. In parallel, a module is dedicated on identifying the connection of "suspicious" devices (i.e., not declared in the system's mapping) as well as any malware that could harm the system or compromise safety through the system's devices. In the context of this manuscript, focus is given on the data security's module "reaction". In detail, if any external effort on breaching the system is detected, then instantaneously, the robot is set to a Cat0 emergency stop. In parallel, the operator is notified

about the security event by the MMIP (i.e. notifications on devices, LED alarm beacons, and alarm sirens) for limiting confusion and for taking the appropriate measures.

3.3. Familiarization of operators to collaborative systems

The perspective of constantly working side by side with robots on a dynamically changing assembly processes, can be quite intimidating and nerve-racking. In addition, operators have to encapsulate complex and enormous volumes of information for keeping up with the modern industrial paradigm and that stresses their adaptation and memorization procedures. In this sense, a novel training framework has been introduced, making the most out of Augmented Reality technology. This framework [44] suggests that novice operators need support either on the use of a new hybrid system, or the execution of a new assembly routine. Subsequently, the discussed training method involves two distinct modes, namely:

- Training mode: This mode involves a “step-by-step” session where all functionalities of the Multi-modal Interaction Pipeline and system resources are analyzed. By running the application, they can navigate in the workstation and receive information about all available resources and controls in augmented format. This training session can also familiarize operators with potential production events (e.g., safety or security incidents, customized product assemblies, etc.) and explain the information they would receive in such cases.
- Assistive mode: This mode introduces operators to the assembly sequence through the use of augmented graphical content and instructions on components of interest that are detected in the real world. Either in textual or 3D CAD format, the assembly process is explained and step by step simulated by recreating robot motions and workstation status.

For both modes, gamification of the sessions is attained for intriguing users on learning new procedures or manufacturing schemes more easily

4. Implementation

The establishment of a seamless human robot collaborative workstation suggests the implementation of a number of modules and their integration as a unified system. Apart from the synchronization of the cooperative agents and their monitoring through a workstation controller, modules of high importance for safety, awareness and well-

being are the implemented (i.e., HRC safety logic, the MMIP, and the gesture-based MG control). The following subsections analyze the deployment and the contribution of each distinct module to the overall solution.

4.1. Physical hybrid cell implementation and software integration

Driven by industrial requirements (refer to Section 5), the workstation, as depicted in Fig. 4, comprises mainly a high payload COMAU NJ130 working in a fenceless environment with a single human operator. The robot is responsible for transferring heavy objects from a buffer area to the assembly line whereas the human operator interacts with the robot for fine tuning its position (whenever is required) and for executing tasks of greater dexterity. Monitoring of safety distances is performed by the safety logic, discussed in Section 4.3. A PILZ Safety Eye sensor has been mounted 5 meters above the cell, where it has a clear top view of the layout and tracks all possible movements and sends back the appropriate signals to the analysis unit. As for the MMIP (refer to Section 4.2.1), wearable and non-wearable devices are implemented to offer to the operator direct access to information streams and robot controls.

Elaborating on additional resources, a custom end-effector is implemented for supporting all requested sensors and interfaces as well as for manipulating different components from a number of product variances. Component grasping is achieved with the use of specially arranged suction cup grippers actuated by two vacuum ejectors. In case of failure, operator’s integrity is preserved by running in parallel two redundant vacuum configurations that are able to securely grasp the component even on their own. In terms of interfaces, the end-effector supports conventional HMIs (refer to 4.2.1) and a hand tracking optical sensor (refer to 4.2.2). The positioning and arrangement of those devices is carefully designed to promote ergonomics, accessibility and collision free object manipulation. The configuration of the buffer area doesn’t have any impact on the collaborative framework since only the robot agent approaches it for retrieving components. Without affecting the generic layout arrangement (i.e., of a robot manipulator that bridges a buffer with a line), the implemented fixtures are designed to support a number of component variances. Similarly, to the end-effector, all product-oriented components are made from materials (e.g. ertalon, soft plastics, etc.) that cannot cause defects on the assembly component. As for the line, a fixture that supports the product (i.e., vehicle chassis) replicates the industrial conveyor that transfers the cars among stations by stopping on each one. Table 2 describes the main components that

Fig. 4. Human High Payload Robot Collaboration workstation and main system modules.

Table 2
Mock-up demonstrator key components.

Component	Description
COMAU NJ130 Robot	Robot for transporting heavyweight components from door fixtures to chassis to be assembled.
COMAU C5G Controller	The brain of the robot, controls all robot actions as well as gripper's functionalities through digital signals
Safety Eye	3D safety camera that detects motion activity through the safety zones
PSS3000 safety PLC	Safety controller that handles all safety eye related signals
PSS4000 safety PLC	Safety PLC that processes all safety signals based on the implemented safety logic.
Robot gripper	Customized design for handling vehicle doors, hoods, tailgates, etc. It is equipped with a hand tracking sensor and a number of HMIs
Leap Motion Controller	Optical sensor for accurate tracking of human hands and hand gestures
Vehicle parts	(a) Chassis, (b) Front door, (c) Rear door
Door fixtures	Buffer area to feed the robot with the vehicle's assembly parts
MMIP hardware	(a) Microsoft's HoloLens 2 for hosting the AR operator's application, (b) Samsung S4 tablet for hosting android operator support application, (c) LG smartwatch for hosting a smartwatch application, (d) LCD screen for MG diagnostics, and (e) LED lights for notifying MG driver status and robot status

were used for the realization of the collaborative cell.

For the communication of all system modules, Robot Operating System (ROS) [40] was used. ROS is an open-source communication middleware that includes a set of tools and libraries for robotic applications. Each module and resource is connected to the rest of the system via a ROS driver, developed in C++ programming language. The synchronization and high-level control of resources during normal operation is performed through a Workcell Controller. This controller is responsible for task assignments and parameter communication as well as for the monitoring of task execution. For robot control, a PDL routine (i.e., program with waypoints, control and monitoring of Digital IOs, etc.) is enabled according to the task assignment that is received by the high level controller. For manual operators, MMIP is used for notifying operator about the ID and name of the task as well as for providing supportive instructions based on the assignment received from the controller. Each "Task Completed" feedback from the operator is communicated to the controller, through any available modality, for informing the system about the successful completion of the executed manual task.

4.2. Human-robot interaction

The objective of the proposed Multi-Modal Interaction Pipeline is ensuring workplace safety and production efficiency by improving awareness of both agents. The following subsections describe the implementation of the advanced multi-modal interaction framework by highlighting the available means of interaction as well as the specifications of each deployed application.

4.2.1. Multi-modal interaction through stationary and wearable devices

For the discussed scenario, the Multi-modal Interaction Pipeline (Fig. 5.a) is realized by deploying: a) an Augmented Reality application, b) an Android tablet application, c) a smartwatch application as well as d) a number of conventional interfaces around the workstation. The MMIP broker, implemented in C#, communicates with the rest of the system via standard ROS messages. Without debunking the system's compatibility or applicability with other communication protocols, all end-applications are communicating with the broker via ROS messages as well. The end-device applications are made in C# and Unity3D game engine.

Aiming to provide an intuitive interaction environment, an Android tablet application was designed (Fig. 5.b). It can be used as a fixed or portable interface, considering that there is autonomy and wireless connectivity. Operators can easily access controls or navigate in application's scenes by touch (voice controls via microphone can also be used). The designed scenes comprise panels with: a) assembly process information (i.e., task ID, task name, textual instructions), b) visual assembly instructions (i.e., figures), c) robot centric information in the form of planned and executed trajectory visualization, and d) ergonomic evaluation results. The level of information detailing is customizable through a dedicated options panel where each user can personalize the application to its needs. In addition, robot controls for pausing or resuming a trajectory are available as buttons.

By overlaying digital information on the physical workstation, the designed AR application provides a highly intuitive application environment. On a similar basis as the tablet application, the same type of information is provided, however in the form of 3D spatially arranged augmented items that the user can interact with. More specifically, inside the operator's point of view (Fig. 6.a) there are augmented buttons, instruction panels, 3D objects, arrows, markers, 3D trajectories, and safety zones. Moreover, augmented notifications are implemented to highlight physical objects upon their detection to ensure that novice operators will retrieve correctly and rapidly the assembly components of interest. Focusing on robot trajectories, an augmented 3D line marks all the waypoints that the robot is about to move and it is online erased during execution. All application's features can be enabled or bypassed depending on the level of experience and the sense of comfort that each

Fig. 5. a) Operator interacting with the robot and main implemented MMIP interfaces, b) Implemented android table application.

Fig. 6. a) Augmented reality application, b) Smartwatch application, and c) conventional HMIs (LED robot state colors).

operator has during normal operation. In addition, this customization also embraces the editing of the augmented objects’ spatial arrangement as the users can virtually grasp them, drag them, and place them wherever seems more apposite. By using Microsoft HoloLens 2 as host device, voice commands, audio signals and gesture recognition modalities are also accessible, meaning that hands-free system control is also available. Audio alarms are valuable for operators when the robot arm is not within their point of view thus, chances of protective stop are further limited due to increased awareness.

In case of autonomy issues or operators prefer plain instructions, more interfaces are also implemented. An application hosted on an Android Smartwatch (Fig. 6.b) provides only “task ID” and “task name” information due to its small sized screen. For task execution feedback, a “task completed” touch button can be accessed in the main scene. In parallel, conventional interfaces are offered as non-wearable devices. Those involve speakers, LCD screens, or LED lights (Fig. 6.c). Speakers

are useful in the case of security incidents as they inform operators about the cause of the unexpected system emergency stop. LED strips, that change color according to the robot status (i.e., moving in auto, safeguard stop, collaborative mode, etc.), are placed at a noticeable area of the cell, whereas LEDs, that present the manual guidance’s driver status, are positioned next to the hand-tracking sensor itself (Fig. 7.c). In the same thinking, near the same sensor, an LCD display is positioned for communicating diagnostics and direct feedback about the velocity goals.

4.2.2. Manual guidance

For achieving contactless hand guiding without the usage of wearable devices, an optical sensor is positioned on the robot’s end-effector, as presented in Fig. 7.a. Ultraleap’s Leap Motion Controller was selected as the most proficient solution for this functionality due to its lightweight design, wide field of view, low cost and high detection performance. More specifically, the controller generates robust and reliable 3D

Fig. 7. Contactless manual guidance: a) main components and interfaces, b) pinching enabling gesture by user, and c) LED based interface for driver’s status feedback.

hand skeletal model in very low latencies and usage certifications [45]. The sensor's official Software Development Kits (SDKs) were used for developing a ROS driver. In detail, the driver communicates confidence, gesture and human palms segment coordinate data, in relevance to the sensor's origin, to the manual guidance server. ROS Transformation libraries were used for prompt transformation of the relative coordinates to global coordinates while solving the required inverse kinematics problem due to the sensor's positioning on the robot's end-effector. After transforming the relative measurements of the sensor to absolute coordinates, the manual guidance module is responsible for converting them to usable robot velocity commands. On the robot side, a routine running inside the robot's controller activates the "Sensor tracking" functionality and waits for velocity inputs. This functionality is provided by the COMAU C5G controller and performs robot velocity control, based on the velocity targets provided by the server via TCP/IP connection.

During normal execution, the task executor activates the sensor driver, MG client and server. Those remain active and operate on closed loop until the collaborative task is completed. For moving the robot, a "pinching" gesture (refer to Fig. 7.b) is used for setting a virtual grip and allowing the communication of data to the server. Due to limitations in controller's accuracy when detecting the hand's orientation, there are two distinct guidance control methods that the user can select through MMIP. The first one focuses on pure translational manipulation that is realized with the help of three PID controllers. Once the activation gesture is detected, the system waits a small amount of time (0.3s) for the user's palm to stabilize, and then stores the relative distance of the palm to the sensor. The relative distance of this virtual grip and the updated pinching hand position generates an error to the PID controllers that is used for the calculation of the target velocities. The second strategy involves the fine-tuning of the end-effector's orientation and uses the sensor for monitoring the control of a virtual "six-directional joystick". Similarly, when a pinching gesture is identified, the translational movements of the arm are translated into digital (i.e. Boolean) inputs that enable velocity control on distinct rotational axis. This way, the operator can guide the robot manipulator in an similar manner as of holding a real grip equipped with a F/T sensor. The PID parameters can be configured for adjusting the robot's response and making it more user friendly. Tuning of all system parameters is possible during runtime without interruption of the control modules by using the dynamic reconfigure API of ROS. The list of configurable parameters contains but is not limited to: a) cut-off confidence threshold, b) required confidence for activating gestures, c) driver timeouts and reconnection retries, d) PID gains, e) velocity thresholds, f) spatial thresholds, and others.

4.3. Safety

4.3.1. Technical specifications of the safety system

The safety system of the demonstrator, as depicted on Fig. 8, deploys some key hardware and software components. The COMAU industrial robot is the core element on which all safety functions act upon. A monitoring system as well as a PILZ safety PLC have been implemented for the real time monitoring of the working area.

The "PILZ SafetyEYE" consists of a sensing camera device, an analysis unit and a PSS3000 PLC. All safety signals coming by or sent to the SafetyEYE are transmitted through the "PILZ PSS3000" safety controller. Nine 3D zone arrangements have been designed with customized dimensions. The safety zones, that scan the area, can dynamically change arrangements according to robot's axis1 orientation or the operation status. Axis_1 position signals are transmitted through the "safety logic" PSS4000 PLC (based on signals coming from the robot controller) and they are sent to the camera's analysis unit allowing an on-the-spot zone transition, that always ensures a safe distance between the human and the robot. The analysis unit receives and processes the sensing camera's image data to identify any violation of the safety zones and communicates feedback, via the PSS3000, to the safety logic's main PLC; about the required robot's state (i.e., speed limitation, safety stop).

Another safety module that is implemented is the COMAU C5G Robosafe system, which is a controller add-on based on BnR safety PLCs. Its purpose is regulating and monitoring robot's position and speed. Through this software, cartesian volumes have been defined as constraints on robot's reach span. This PLC has direct access to the robot driver's power supply, forcing category 1 stop in case a joint exceeds the volumetric boundaries.

Focusing on the main logic's PLC, the PSS4000 instantaneously changes the robot's state, either by slowing it down at a maximum collaborative speed of 250mm/s, or even completely stopping its motion if deemed necessary (Category 2 stop). This is achieved by monitoring all related safety signals and communicating outputs to the robot's controller. When in safeguard stop, the operator needs to exit the workspace and reset robot's activities by simply pressing a reset button. This way it is ensured that the operator is physically presented outside robot's active perimeter, avoiding any possible entrapment inside the safety zones.

Finally, the system is equipped with a cyber-security protection module. Upon identification of an external malware intrusion, this module sends a message to an externally installed PLC. This message is communicated through an isolated network and triggers signals that are wired to the PSS4000. The former one causes a robot safeguard stop (Category 1) to prevent any safety incidents caused by cyber-attack.

Fig. 8. Implemented Safety System.

4.3.2. Risk assessment

The risk assessment takes into account all involved apparatus in situ, such as robot, gripper, chassis, doors, door fixtures, controller. During the different assembly phases of the collaborative scenario, various hazards can occur. The risk assessment summarizes the most probable ones that might happen in a specific time increment of the process. In Table 3, the provisional safety hazards among with their correlated assembly phases as well as their respective safety mitigation methods are enlisted. The established technical equipment described in paragraph 4.3.1, addresses all these risks in a human-centric manner. More details are given in the following subsection.

4.3.3. Safety and security system implementation

In principle, and according to the risks identified, the manufacturing process can be separated in two fundamental phases. Phase 1 involves the grasping and transportation of the products by the robot, where physical presence of the operator is irrelevant and, thus, nonexistent. Whereas in Phase 2, the operator enters the working space to guide the robot during the joining operations. During the first phase, an accurate mapping and monitoring of the working area is requisite to track all probable intrusions with the use of the safe camera system. According to the SSM method that is applied in this case, the distance between the robot and the operator implies different robot speed adjustments. In detail, two safety zones are introduced around the robot (Fig. 9), namely: a) warning zone (yellow) and b) danger zone (red). An intrusion of the yellow zone slows down the robot to a prescribed maximum speed of 250mm/s, as suggested by the ISO regulations (ISO 10218-2/5.11.5.4 – working inside the warning zone). In case of a red zone intrusion, the minimum safety distance has been violated, thus robot instantly stops its operation while keeping its motors actuated (Category 2 Stop). The shaping (arrangement and dimensioning) of these three-dimensional safety zones ensures that no human operator can enter the robot workspace without been traced and that the required separation distances during robot movement are obeyed.

Regarding the second phase, as suggested by the ISO standards (ISO/TS 15066:2010/5.5.2.2), a 20mm/s speed is set during the manual guidance of the robot. When in manual guidance mode, the robot is set to a Category 2 stop, with its actuators still in drive-on. The manual guidance module implements a range of safety features to prevent accidental movement of the robot. More specifically, the gesture detection is coupled with a delayed threshold to confidently validate the gesture for a minimal amount of time before starting the guidance. A high frequency watchdog timer is constantly checking the existence of up-to-date sensor data and verifies the existence of proper communication with the controller. Additionally, the detection confidence values are monitored, and the raw sensor data are utilized only when detection

confidence exceeds a certain threshold value. Finally, a plausibility detection algorithm, that detects unusually fast or impossible movements of the operator's hands, has also been implemented. In all kinds of uncertainties, the system enforces the robot to a Category 2 stop and resets the manual guidance module to a safe state.

4.4. Operator training through augmented reality

As discussed, the training framework aims on supporting novice operators through two distinct training sessions. The augmented reality application, developed in Unity Game engine, is hosted in Microsoft HoloLens 2. The session of the "training mode" (Fig. 10.a) recreates a walkthrough experience, on which the operator is instructed about specific aspects of the collaborative system. As soon as the operator fully comprehends the provided info, a "next" button is available in order to proceed on the next training scene. By the end of the session, operators will be tutored on how they can interact with available resources, as well as how to use the MMIP and its customization features. On the other hand, the "assistive mode" (Fig. 10.b) is oriented on presenting the assembly process of interest. On each step, information is presented as augmented paneling instructions, work piece visualizations, guiding arrows and pointers, virtual process simulations of relative movements and physical object identifications.

5. Case study

The designed framework and the developed modules towards seamless human – (high-payload) robot collaboration are assessed on a use case originating from the automotive industry. A hybrid cell implemented at LMS facilities was used for evaluating the system's performance through a series of tests. The scenario focuses on the assembly of body parts (i.e., doors, bonnet, tailgates) on vehicle chassis heading towards the paint workshop. In current practice this process is completely manual and takes place for a series of vehicle variants. On each cycle, operators manipulate objects, weighing up to 15kg, by retrieving them from buffers, by transferring them for a few meters, and by attaching them on the vehicle chassis. The main challenges of this scenario can be summarized as: a) strenuous pick and place operations that could cause musculoskeletal problems, b) dual peg in hole joining process (i.e., door-chassis) via heavy object handling, c) fluctuations in Key Performance Indicators due to human errors and fatigue.

On business level, the automation of this process grants opportunities for higher efficiency and repeatability. Nevertheless, the assembly of multiple vehicle variances and the inexistence of high accuracy fixtures presents handicaps, that only human dexterity and cognition capabilities can address in a robust and cost-efficient manner. In this direction, semi-automation is attained by allocating the retrieving and the manipulation of heavy components to a high-payload robot whereas the human operator will be responsible for the non-strenuous and delicate operations. In detail, operators will: a) interact with the robot agent in order to precisely guide the robot during the peg in hole operation, and afterwards b) secure the assembly by putting and fastening a screw on each hinge. The complete assembly scenario is step-by-step described in Table 4 and presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. Human integrity and safety are preserved by the discussed safety framework with the most important feature to be the fenceless 3D safety zone monitoring by the Safety Eye. With the same objective in mind, the design of the layout and workstation's components (e.g., fixtures, grippers, etc.) took place. For seamless human robot communication, the Multi-Modal Interaction Pipeline is implemented with numerous modalities available through wearables (e.g., AR headset, tablet, smart-watch) or stationary (e.g., tablet, screens, LEDs, LCD, beacon, alarms) devices.

Table 3
Identified hazards.

Hazard	Description	Safety method	Assembly phases
1	Impact with robot	SSM	Product grasping & transport
2	Impact with robot's gripper	SSM + HG	Product grasping, transport & assembly
3	Impact on product	SSM + HG	Product transport & assembly
4	Trapped in between robot's gripper and door fixtures	SSM	Product grasping
5	Trapped in between robot's gripper and chassis	HG + SMS	Product assembly
6	Trapped behind robot	SSM	Product assembly
7	Trapped in robot joints	HG + SMS	Product assembly
8	Product detachment from gripper	SMS	Product assembly
9	Unauthorized personnel entrance	SSM	Product grasping, transport & assembly

Fig. 9. SafetyEYE safety zone monitoring: a) no intrusion, b) yellow zone violation, c) violation of red zone.

Fig. 10. AR Training application: a) Training mode, and b) Assistive mode.

Table 4
Use-case scheduling.

Process No.	Previous Process	Process Name	Resource	Tool
R01	-	Robot approaching buffer, grasping rear door and transferring it to chassis	Robot	Gripper
HR01	R01	Operator guiding robot for positional fine-tuning	Operator, Robot	MGS
H01	HR01	Operator performing fastening activities	Operator	Screwdriver
R02	H01	Robot releasing assembled part and returning to home position	Robot	-
H02	H01	Operator closes rear door and exits workcell	Operator	-
R03	R02	Robot approaching buffer, grasping front door and transferring it to chassis	Robot	Gripper
HR02	R04	Operator guiding robot for positional fine-tuning	Operator, Robot	MGS
H03	HR02	Operator performing fastening activities	Operator	Screwdriver
R04	H03	Robot releasing assembled part and returning to home position	Robot	-
H04	H03	Operator closes front door and exits workcell	Operator	-

6. Results & discussion

The developed testbed has been evaluated in terms of usability and performance. Two of the most valuable metrics, which strongly interest the industrial sector, are the impact on a) the cycle time of the entire process, as well as b) the worker’s ergonomics and well-being. The following paragraphs present: a) a detailed breakdown of the total cycle time results, b) an analytical ergonomic evaluation of human activities, and c) an assessment of the system’s usability.

6.1. Cycle time analysis

The contribution of the collaborative framework, regarding the production’s cycle time, is evaluated by measuring and comparing the respective assembly cycle durations of the hybrid cell with the exact same manual process. A thorough breakdown of all task’s individual timings is performed for both manual and hybrid concepts, as seen in Table 5. After performing 40 consecutive cycles, tasks durations are normalized into mean values. The difference between the cycle times of the manual and the semi-automated solutions is almost marginal. In detail, 116.3s is the cycle time of the collaborative scenario whereas 114.7s is the cycle time of the manually performed assembly. The main difference between those two processes is that component transportation does not require any human interference leading to a 25% human operator idle time. This gap creates an opportunity for introducing more added value operations in the same of nearby workstations that the human operator could be involved. The projected mean values achieved on the HRC assembly per task can also be found in Fig. 13, bounded by the minimum and the maximum reported times for each

Fig. 11. Assembly process PERT Chart.

task. As expected, the marginal deviation on all robot tasks is insignificant, justified by the high robot's repeatability. Large deviations, on the other hand, are reported when the human factor is introduced, especially in the collaborative tasks. Overall, the mean value is found to be closer to the lower bound, since higher duration values are the result of infrequent events (like unintended tool or fastener dropping or misalignments during the peg in hole process that would need a switch to the manual guidance's rotational mode). On experimental basis, the hybrid system's cycle time was further reduced by almost 4 seconds by increasing the robot speed thresholds. However, the safety zones were enlarged, and the robot motions started to intimidate operators mostly due to the increased motor noises.

Based on the analysis presented on Table 6, robot is utilized for most of the process by transferring components, or by contributing on their assembly during hand guiding (over 97%). There are over 20 seconds counted on which the robot stands still passively (i.e. supporting components till fastening is completed), meaning that a robot actuation efficiency of 83% is observed.

6.2. Ergonomics analysis

The goal of this ergonomics analysis is to evaluate operator's postures for quantifying the levels of discomfort and any risk of injury or long-term musculoskeletal issues. For this study, AAWS method was used as it can normalize events and postures based on their duration and also consider additional parameters such as material handling or force application. Another aspect that made this method appealing is that analytical evaluation results could be validated in simulation environment. More specifically, both manual and semi-automated scenarios were simulated in DELMIA V5. ErgoToolkit, which is an ergonomics evaluation software extension of DELMIA, developed by LMS [46], was used for evaluating ergonomics via AAWS.

Focusing on the evaluation, AAWS [47] generates a score that sums: a) a postural score, resulting from human's postures and their time-related impact on the whole cycle, b) an action forces score, resulting from loads on human limbs, and c) a material handling score, resulting for object manipulation. A low total score (<25) suggests that no workstation redesign is needed, whereas medium (26÷50) or high scores demand workstation modifications in long term or immediately, in respect. For the discussed case study, the ergonomics improvement after the implementation of the collaborative cell is exceptional. In detail, a completely manual process reached a score value over 54, in contrary the collaborative solution managed only 4, as presented Table 7. For the collaborative scenario, the score is mostly affected by the fastening process where operators still have to bend slightly bend their whist as well as HG where they have to raise their hand for a number of seconds.

This significant improvement comes from the execution of all strenuous tasks by the robot. Both transferring of doors and joining through peg in hole processes are characterized by their high physical requirements as presented in Fig. 14. Given the repeatable handling of 15kg components for more than 50 times per hour, this working place is excluded for operators of less muscular physique or disabilities.

Subsequently, the proposed collaborative system increases job openness and promotes practices like job rotation. This is because less physical male or female workers as well as people with disabilities can achieve and maintain high productivity levels with low fatigue. On business level, job openness, job rotation and low fatigue can contribute also to other aspects like high consistent quality, productivity, and less waste. Therefore, key industrial requirements are fulfilled signifying that industrial implementation could be reached.

6.3. System usability and acceptance

During the validation of the system, a series of experimental trials were performed by a group of users/operators that were unfamiliar with the implemented collaborative framework. The goal of those experiments was to assess the usability and acceptance of the system and identify possible shortcomings. Twelve operators worked and collaborated with the robot by assembling doors to vehicle chassis. The age and gender distribution of the targeted group are shown in Fig. 15. More than half of the statistical population was between eighteen to thirty-four years of age, while male subjects were the vast majority that were asked to assist on the experimental trials.

Apart from workstation and resource design, those usability tests assess the performance of the Multi-Modal Interaction Pipeline. After testing from each individual, the operators were asked to fill anonymously a questionnaire according to the System Usability Scale (SUS) [48]. This scale determines the usability of a system through ten standard questions by generating a total score. All scores, seen in Table 8, indicate that the devices are comprehensive, flexible and accurate.

According to the findings, the proposed interface proved to be a valuable tool for the overall performance and awareness. The users expressed that it is interpreted as a personalized virtual assistance that guides the operator through the entire process by displaying critical information on demand. The availability of customization options as well as the buttonless controls (i.e. that permitted hands-free system control) were noticed as pleasing additions that increased their efficiency. The instructions provided per task were intuitive and guided the users in all aspects of the process. Elaborating on the interfaces and the modalities that were used during runtime, users expressed that the Augmented Reality application is the most intuitive one. However, this technology still needs to overcome some comfort issues that the headsets come up with. It is noteworthy that none of the operators disabled the safety related content (i.e. safety zones, robot trajectories). As expressed, there were no digital items that interfered in their working area and distracted them during manual operations. This wasn't the case however for two users, who disabled the graphical instructions (i.e. arrows); since there was no added value given their advanced level of expertise. As for the human system interaction, originally, there was a strong preference on the augmented buttons, however this was overwhelmed with a gradual tendency of using the voice commands. Referring to the tablet interface, the majority of users (10 out of 12) discussed that they would maintain fully explanatory instructions even when they fully comprehend the process. The remainder of them would disable the graphical content on the following period if the task IDs and textual instructions

Fig. 12. Use case demonstrator at LMS facilities: Step by Step depictive presentation of the assembly process.

were found to be sufficient. Finally, the smartwatch application was found to be very convenient and practical, however it was not favoured since the AR and table interfaces were more direct. A comment about this application was that instead of having a “Task completed” button, a “double full screen tap” would be even more convenient. All users expressed that the smartwatch application would be fully used if the AR headset runs out of battery or if users become fully proficient on the

assembly operation or the usage of the cell.

Apart from the MMIP, users also expressed their impressions on the safety system and the overall enhancement of working conditions. In detail, the implemented safety logic managed to maintain users’ sense of safety at high levels without any trust issues. The designed safety zone arrangements as well as their visualization through AR headset provided the required confidence and awareness for fenceless coexistence.

Table 5
Cycle time analysis of manual assembly (left) and HRC assembly (right).

Operation	Duration [s]	Deviation [s]	Task	Operation	Duration [s]	Deviation [s]
Lift and transport rear door	10,2	[-2.1, +3.3]	R01	Transport rear door	16,3	[-0.3, +0.3]
Assembly rear door	31,6	[-7.4, +17.2]	HR01	Manual guidance	29,7	[-3.1, +12]
Fastening	12,7	[-1.1, +1.6]	H01	Fastening	7,9	[-0.3, +3.9]
Close door	3,1	[-0.3, +0.3]	R02	Release rear door	3,6	[-0.3, +0.3]
Lift and transport front door	9,6	[-2, +6.1]	H02	Close rear door and exit	2,1	[-0.7, +2.1]
Assembly front door	31,8	[-10.4, +12.5]	R03	Transport front door	12,8	[-0.3, +0.3]
Fastening	12,4	[-1.5, +1.4]	HR02	Manual guidance	30,3	[-2.1, +8.1]
Close door	3,3	[-0.4, +0.3]	H03	Fastening	7,8	[-0.8, +2.9]
TOTAL	114.7		R04	Release front door	3,6	[-0.3, +0.3]
			H04	Close front door and exit	2,2	[-0.5, +1.0]
			TOTAL	TOTAL	116.3	

Fig. 13. HRC assembly time breakdown of tasks.

Table 6
Total production cycle performance.

Overall metrics	
Cycle time	approx. 116 sec
Robot utilization	approx. 97%
Robot idle time	approx. 3%
Robot efficiency	approx. 83%
Robot wait time	approx. 20 sec

Table 7
Ergonomic Analysis Results.

AAWS scores	Manual process	Collaborative assembly
Postural score	5	2.5
Action Forces score	4	0
Material Handling score	45	1.5
Total	54	4

In addition, a very important feature of the robotic system was the contactless manual guidance. More specifically, users did not communicate any difficulties during the peg in hole joining operations since the robot’s response was optimal without delays or overshoots. Out of 12 operators, 5 subjects (i.e. four men, and one woman) were also called to execute the same process completely manual. Those described that the ergonomic optimization of working conditions is exceptional, whereas in the case of the woman, she was not successful in assembling the second

door under the risk of musculoskeletal harm. It is noted that after the semi-automation of the scenario, none of the gender or age attributes didn’t seem to give any noteworthy advantage to the subjects in terms of efficiency or usability metrics. During runtime, the orientation that the doors were delivered presented high accuracy, thus the rotational manual guidance mode was a feature of no much use. During standalone experiments, users didn’t highlight any difficulty on using the joystick mode, however they recommended the implementation of augmented items to visualize the limits of the “virtual handle”.

An important role in the sense of “improved working conditions” and “easiness of system usage” played the implemented training framework. Both modes drastically reduced the chances of mistakes and more steep learning curves were achieved.

7. Conclusions and future work

This paper discusses a holistic approach for the implementation of human robot collaborative systems. The novelty of the solution lies on the establishment of efficient and safe collaboration between operators and high-payload industrial robot arms, as inspired by industrial requirements and needs. Having as baseline operator safety and acceptance, modules for safety, seamless interaction, direct robot guiding, and training are introduced. More specifically, the system’s safety logic supports: a) a dynamically reconfigurable safety zone monitoring system (for speed and separation monitoring), b) hand guiding, and c) safeguarding against cyber security incidents. Effectual human robot communication is established through the implemented MMIP. This

Fig. 14. Ergonomics optimization: a) automated heavyweight component handling instead of manual transferring, and b) effortless hand guiding instead of physical intensive peg in hole handling.

Fig. 15. : a) Age group distribution, b) Gender group distribution.

Table 8
SUS analysis results.

User	Score	User	Score
1	82.5	7	65
2	85	8	92.5
3	72.5	9	85
4	82.5	10	87.5
5	87.5	11	80
6	90	12	85

interaction framework communicates robot-centric information and instructions about the assembly process execution and optimum behaviour in the workspace. The availability of numerous customizable interfaces and different interaction modalities promotes the personalization of the system according to each subject’s needs. Apart from MMIP’s controlling interfaces, a contactless gesture-based hand-guiding system is implemented allowing accurate direct handling of robot position using optical data. For ensuring rapid inclusion of users, an augmented reality-based application is developed, for performing training sessions that can introduce operators to the MMIP as well as the assembly sequence itself.

After testing time-related, ergonomics and usability9 KPIs, the results indicate that high payload robots can rather support operators than compete them. Applications where heavyweight components are involved usually are excluded from hybrid automation due to the low payload capabilities of collaborative robots. However, those scenarios are ideal for demonstrating the potential of ergonomics and working condition improvement that collaborative systems can offer. By

dispatching heavyweight component handling operations to robots and assigning dexterous operations to human workers, the implemented system accomplished the set KPI requirements and managed to diminish any risks of musculoskeletal issues. The challenging peg in hole operations were addressed by the implemented manual guidance system that presented high accuracy and fine response. Individuals that tested the system witnessed that working conditions are very much improved and that the implemented MMIP strengthened their sense of comfort, confidence and awareness. The developed AR-based training framework contributed to system acceptance and rapid adaptation of users given also the limited number of available normal operation tests per individual. On business level, the execution of strenuous tasks by the robot agents contributes to job openness and easier job rotation. Operators of less muscular physique or workers with special needs can now effectively be allocated to hybrid workstations of this type.

In short term, the collaborative framework will be tested on the end-user’s industrial premises. Future work of the authors will focus on the optimization of the collaborative solution by expanding the features of the implemented technical solutions. Introduction of additional interaction modalities and devices will be investigated to accommodate more operator preferences. The gesture based manual guidance system will be enhanced by introducing a hybrid controller that also fuses force-torque feedback as an additional barrier against product defects. Last but not least, standardization activities will be closely followed and supported for contributing into making such robotic systems in industry more and more conventional.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Dionisis Andronas: Methodology, Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Emmanouil Kampourakis:** Methodology, Software, Conceptualization, Investigation. **Giorgos Papadopoulos:** Software, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Katerina Bakopoulou:** Software, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Panagiotis Stylianos Kotsaris:** Software, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **George Michalos:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Sotiris Makris:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Supplementary materials

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